

ZEPHIRO

*Zero Emission Pollution In
Real Time Operation*

Purpose of the document

Present the **machine** and its **technological innovations**, highlighting the **new solutions** it introduces to the industry

Illustrate the **functional, environmental, social, and economic benefits** of the **new technology**, emphasizing the **optimization of operational performance** and the **positive impact on various societal dimensions**

Demonstrate how the **machine represents a significant step towards innovation in the field of treatments**, **improving efficiency** and **supporting institutional objectives** of progress and sustainability in the sector

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Current critical issues in crop protection treatments and introduction of our solutions

Presentation of cutting-edge technologies to improve crop protection

Benefits and advantages deriving from the adoption of these innovative solutions, both on an economic, environmental and social level

Current problems

Major issues

- **Current crop treatments** often **damage the environment** and threaten **biodiversity** with their high **toxicity**.
- **Consume large quantities of water and energy** resources, exacerbating the scarcity of natural resources.
- The high **costs of management** and application of **treatments** represent a significant **burden** for **farmers**.
- **Traditional practices** are increasingly **ineffective** due to growing **pathogen** and **disease resistance**.
- There is a **serious risk to human health** from **exposure to pesticide residues** and other agricultural **chemicals**.

AIR DRIFT

Improper air management can cause drift, carrying chemicals into unwanted areas resulting in risks to the environment, animals and people

DRIPPING

The dripping of pesticides or fertilizers, caused by drops that are too large or overdoses, wastes product and contaminates soil and water, affecting the treatment

OPERATING AND MANAGEMENT COSTS

The costs of treatment in crop protection include pesticides and gasoline; the management cover pest monitoring, personnel training, for an integrated pest management implementation.

LACK OF LABOR

The lack of labor in agriculture is due to factors such as low wages and demanding working conditions, which scare potential workers, making the sector less attractive

Caffini's solutions...our reply(s)!

FAN AIRFLOW CONTROL

- The **subdivision into several blower organs** allows the machine to adapt to the phenological development of the plants
- It **operates differentially based on the growth stages of the plants**
- It follows a **vertical distribution profile** for precise operation

DROPLET SIZE CONTROL

- Pulse Width Modulation (**PWM**) **nozzles** ensure **timely and consistent droplet delivery**
- **Each blower** is equipped with **two PWM nozzles**.
- The **nozzles operate at a working frequency of 10Hz**, guaranteeing precise application

FULL ELECTRIC SOLUTIONS

- **Complete electrification** offers full control over every component, **enhancing the precision and efficiency of the system**
- The **electric pump** can independently **regulate the number of revolutions**, ensuring optimal performance without relying on the tractor's engine speed
- **This system's independence** from the tractor's engine revolutions **allows for more consistent and reliable operation**
- The **elimination of the cardan shaft** simplifies the setup and reduces maintenance requirements

AI CAMERA VISION SYSTEMS

- **Agronomic control is managed by an advanced RGB-D sensor system**, which utilizes **AI-based algorithms** for precise analysis
- These **algorithms analyze the crop in real time**, allowing for dynamic adaptation of the treatment to suit current conditions
- This **real-time analysis and adaptation improve the effectiveness of the treatment**, ensuring that it targets the crop accurately
- By **adapting treatments based on real-time data**, the system significantly reduces resource waste, making the **process more efficient and sustainable**

ISOBUS

- The **ISOBUS interface** provides the operator with **full interoperability, allowing seamless integration** with various equipment and systems
- This **interface ensures ease of use, simplifying the operation** of the machine for the operator
- The **ISOBUS system eliminates the need for complex adjustments** during operational processes, **streamlining workflow and increasing efficiency**
- By **standardizing communication between devices**, the **ISOBUS interface enhances the overall functionality and flexibility of the machine**

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The revolution: ZEPHIRO

Principal aspects of multi-blowers solution

Multi-blowers solution

- Regulation with multiple degrees of freedom, allowing for highly flexible and precise control over various operational parameters
- Configuration options include setups with 6, 8, or more blowers, providing adaptability to different scales and types of agricultural applications
- Independent management of each individual blower, enabling spot spraying for targeted treatment and optimized resource use
- Automatic closure mechanism activates in case of failures or absence of vegetation, ensuring safety and preventing unnecessary spraying
- Differentiation between left and right sides, allowing for tailored treatment that matches the specific needs of each side of the crop
- Vertical differentiation, offering precise control over the vertical distribution of treatments to match the height and growth stage of the plants
- Each blower is equipped with 2 PWM nozzles, enhancing the uniformity and consistency of droplet distribution for more effective treatment coverage

Blowers particular – general

Blowers particular – section view

Based on *ANSI B175.2*

Speed	Air Force on ANSI Target	Air velocity	Air Flow
20.000 rpm	11 N	47 m/s	730 m3/h

48 Volt power supply
 Brushless motor around ~800W
 Integrated control electronics
 Real-time diagnostics

Ugelli PWM

- SINGLE NOZZLE
- DIFFERENT DROPLET SIZE
- CONSTANT PRESSURE

Full electric implement

- The complete 48V electrification offers full control over every component: the electric pump, blowers and nozzles

The **functional advantages** offered by the ease and speed of **control**, achieved by the **complete electrification** of ZEPHIRO, lead to **more efficient** and **precise operations**

This solution allowed to eliminate the entire mechanical transmission. The **development of ZEPHIRO** harmonises with the **new tractors**, which are **capable of supplying electricity directly to implements**. In the case of **conventional tractors**, a **generator can be installed** on the PTO to produce the necessary energy

A **solution** which is **scalable and modular** with further technologies for an **eco-sustainable world!**

AI vision system

Vision system

- A configuration of 2 to 4 cameras efficiently covers multiple cultures, ensuring comprehensive monitoring and management of diverse crops. This setup is overseen by a single MASTER ECU for streamlined control
- The MASTER ECU processes all incoming data and provides real-time signals on the CANBUS line, enabling precise control of liquid and air percentages for optimal treatment application
- The system ensures optimal resource application, significantly enhancing agricultural practices by maximizing efficiency and effectiveness in crop management
- Its scalability and advanced data handling capabilities make it an essential tool for modern farming, offering adaptability and precision to meet the evolving needs of the agricultural sector

Stereo Camera AI vision

Provides **varied data for better insights**

Operates at night

Scalable with **AI algorithms**

Calculates **canopy shape**

Able to **detects Flavescence Dorée, Downy mildew, Powdery mildew etc**

Counts fruits and flowers

